

Electrical Transport of Nb-Doped MoS₂ Homojunction P-N

Diode: Investigating NDR and Avalanche Effect

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Abstract

Two-dimensional (2D) materials provide a suitable platform for field-effect transistors (FETs) to achieve low-power electronics for various analogue and digital device applications. However, to realize high-performance devices, the layer's number selection and angle-controlled stacking of various 2D materials remained a critical challenge. In this study, the thickness-modulated homojunction p-n diode manifested by Nb-doped MoS₂ was investigated. The homojunction configuration eliminates interface traps without requiring external interface control, offering a major benefit in device performance. The devices showed excellent rectifying behavior with a rectification ratio of $\sim 10^4$ and the lowest ideality factor ($\eta=1.23$). Interestingly, our findings revealed the field-dependent occurrence of negative differential resistance (NDR) at low temperatures, a phenomenon that holds significant interest in electronic applications. Furthermore, the devices show photoresponsivity of $1.09 \times 10^3 \text{ A/W}$, an external quantum efficiency (EQE) of $2.16 \times 10^5\%$ and detectivity (D^*) 7.5×10^{10} Jones. Moreover, the study explored the electrical breakdown phenomenon that result from avalanche multiplication at low voltages in Nb-Doped MoS₂-based devices with varying layer thicknesses. This meticulous study provides a method for creating high-performance avalanche photodetectors in addition to illuminating the tunable photoexcitation process. Thus, our study demonstrates a simple and robust method to probe carrier multiplication in homojunction p-n diodes, embarking the role of 2D materials in avalanche devices.

Keywords: MoS₂, Homojunction, Photodetector, Avalanche Effect, NDR Effect

Introduction

In the age of the Internet of Things (IoT), one of the biggest challenges that scientists are facing is lowering the power consumption of electronic devices [1]. The exceptional electrical and optical characteristics of transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs) have garnered significant attention. TMDCs are excellent prospects for field-effect transistors (FETs), LED's, and photovoltaics due to their atomic thickness, high carrier mobility, and tunable band gap [2]. Likewise, the van der Waals (vdW) p-n junctions have been showing a vibrant contribution to real-world applications of TMDC layered semiconductors [3]. Both the transfer method and direct epitaxial growth have been exploited to establish several vdW's 2D heterostructures, [4] including graphene/h-BN [5], MoS₂/graphene [6], WS₂/MoS₂ [7], GaTe/ReSe₂ [8], WSe₂/SnS₂ [9] and MoS₂/WSe₂ heterojunctions [10]. The tunnel FETs (T-FETs), which are based on carbon nanotube tube (CNT) [11] and oxide/IV [12] semiconductors, have been thoroughly investigated. Two-dimensional (2D) materials present an optimal opportunity for T-FETs due to their unique properties [13]. The short tunnelling path at the vdW interface enhances the on-state current, while the absence of dangling bonds at the vdW hetero-interface helps to minimize charge carrier scattering, thereby improving device performance [14]. Unlike other TMDCs, molybdenum disulfide (MoS₂) possesses a tunable band gap, making it possible to create multipurpose nanodevices [15]. As the layer number of MoS₂ drops, its bandgap rises, and it shifts from an indirect (1.3 eV) to a direct bandgap (1.8 eV) structure. Because of significant mobility, efficient stability and suitable abundance [16], MoS₂ has been regarded as a potential TMDC candidate for upcoming nano-electronic devices, including phototransistors [17] and short-channel transistors [18]. Due to low dark current and better photocurrent, MoS₂ has recently been sparking as a viable photodetector [19]. It has been recently shown that ferroelectric polarization or an external field can increase photoresponse by further depleting electron carriers and suppressing the dark current. Another tactic to enhance the photocurrent is to create junctions, where the integrated electric field makes it easier to separate the photogenerated electron and hole [17]. The photoresponse was boosted from visible to near-infrared by the extra interband excitation [20]. The homojunction helps to reduce interlayer scattering which reduces dark current and a generates quick response as compared to heterojunctions where the lattice

mismatches will impede photoexcitation and transportation of charges which can minimize the photoresponse [17]. For instance, *Lu et al* [21] constructed a MoS₂ p–n homojunction using nitrogen plasma doping technique and showed that the responsivity increased from 7.5 mA/W to 48.5 A/W. Though, MoS₂ typically exhibits n-type conductivity because of the favored sulfur (S) vacancy. P-type MoS₂ can be prepared using a number of techniques, including chemical transport technique [22], ion implantation [23], direct sulfurization [24], and chemical vapor deposition (CVD). For large-scale growth, CVD has been utilized extensively to examine Nb doping, using NbCl₅ [25], NaCl mixed Nb₂O₅ [17] as the Nb precursors. Nb-doped MoS₂ has also recently been grown using the liquid precursor based on niobium oxalate hydrate [26]. Nevertheless, the mobility of the synthesized Nb-doped MoS₂ is typically poor. Furthermore, as reported in various study, the effect of Nb doping exhibits significant variations, which is likely attributed to the poor quality of the doped film and challenging doping arrangements, therefore the precise crystal growth of Nb-doped MoS₂ is still an issue.

Added to this, several initiatives have been undertaken to explore impact ionization in avalanche transistors constructed from 2D materials. Avalanche FETs [27] are becoming significant in electronics owing to their capacity to improve device performance and stability. The avalanche effect is a phenomenon that occurs when there is a significant increase in current resulting from the impact ionization of charge carriers (holes and electrons) within the material. This happens when an electric field (E-Field) over the p-n junction is sufficiently intense, resulting in a fast multiplication of charge carriers. Furthermore, an electrical breakdown is influenced by the electronic band alignment and energy bandgap of 2D materials-based devices [28]. The electrical breakdown in 2D-based FETs can be influenced by the thickness of the channel, owing to its quantum confinement, which facilitates a tunable band configuration. Consequently, a detailed study of the mechanisms that drive the electrical breakdown in MoS₂ under minor electric fields is essential. However, limited information has been revealed related to the avalanche effect of MoS₂ at strong electric fields, as the atomically thin MoS₂ channel layer exhibits constrained thermal energy dissipation capacity, resulting in thermal breakdown [29]. The high heat resistance of insulating substrate materials, such as SiO₂ and polymer dielectrics, exacerbates this problem [30]. Consequently, the majority of electrical findings

in MoS₂-based FETs have been conducted inside the linear regime using low source-drain bias to avert thermal failure due to Joule heating ^[31]. However, power-efficient and stable avalanche FETs at room temperature are still needed in this era of advanced technology. Thus, the controlled large-scale crystal growth of Nb-doped MoS₂ has remained a problem. Therefore, the NDR effect, photoexcitation characteristics and avalanche effect of Nb: MoS₂ homojunction are still unclear.

Herein, we investigate the lateral p-n homojunction fabricated from Nb-doped MoS₂ crystals. Our findings indicate that, at low temperatures, a negative differential resistance (NDR) persists. This indicates external field may effectively achieve the TFET process under type-III band configuration, suggesting that band-to-band tunnelling (BTBT) is the primary mechanism due to the optimum interface. The tunability of photoresponse and detectivity in response to the applied voltage, wavelength, and light power have been comprehensively examined in the Nb-doped MoS₂ homojunction-based device. We also investigated the electrical breakdown phenomena in Nb-doped MoS₂ devices with various layer thicknesses, which arise from avalanche multiplication. This comprehensive work presents a methodology for fabricating high-performance avalanche photodetectors while elucidating the controlled photoexcitation mechanism.

Experimental method

Synthesis and Device Fabrication: The bulk crystals of Nb-doped MoS₂ were grown via the chemical vapor transport (CVT) process in a quartz glass ampoule via MoCl₅ as a transport agent. For the synthesis were used molybdenum powder (99.999%, -100 mesh, Quality Key Materials, Co. China) sulfur granules (1-6 mm, 99.9999%, Wuhan Tuocai Technology Co., China) and niobium (-100 mesh, 99.9%, Beijing Metallurgy and Materials Technology Co., China) together with molybdenum pentachloride (99.9%, Strem, USA) as a source of chlorine acting as a transport agent. In the quartz ampoule (50x250mm) were placed 50g of precursors corresponding to MO_{0.997}Nb_{0.03}S₂ composition together with 1.0g of MoCl₅. Sulfur were used in 2at% excess towards stoichiometry. The ampoule were melt sealed with oxygen-hydrogen welding torch under high vacuum using oil diffusion pump with liquid nitrogen trap (base pressure under 1x10⁻³ Pa). The ampoule

was first heated in a muffle furnace at 500 °C for 25 h, at 600 °C for 50 h and at 800 °C for 50 h. The heating and cooling rate was 1 °C min⁻¹ and between each temperature step, the mixture was homogenized by shaking for up to 5 min. The generated polycrystalline disulfide was kept in a two-zone horizontal crystal growth furnace for CVT growth. First, the growth zone was heated at 1000 °C and the source zone was placed at 700 °C. After the passing of 50 h, the thermal gradient was inverted, the source zone was placed at 1000 °C and the growth zone changed to 900 °C over a time of 10 days. At the final stage, the growth zone temperature was kept at 500 °C for 2 h to eliminate the transport medium and excess sulfur from the growth zone. Above 50% of starting material were transported over the time of 10 days. The ampules were open in the glove box (argon-filled) and the crystals were placed in the inert atmosphere. The thick-thin layers of Nb-Doped MoS₂ were attained by fundamental mechanical exfoliation techniques, which is a simple scotch tape method. The thick-thin homojunction was transferred on Si/SiO₂ by a simple dry transfer method with the help of PDMS. We have used Si/SiO₂ as substrate with silver (Ag) pre-patterned as the metal contacts. After transferring the Nb-doped MoS₂ on the Si/SiO₂/Ag substrates, the devices were annealed for two hours at 200 °C under high vacuum to make better contact between metal and Nb-doped MoS₂ flakes. Natural MoS₂ crystals were used as an undoped n-type conductive samples (origin from Krupka, Krusne Hory, Czechia).

Measurements

SIMS Characterization: Secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS) test was performed by means of a CAMECA IMS SC Ultra apparatus with a cesium ion source and positive detector polarity. All signals were recorded as CsX⁺ ions, which are considered semi-quantitative due to suppression of the matrix effects [32]. Measurements were conducted on five crystals, with elemental composition analyzed at depths of 0.1 μm, 1 μm, 10 μm, and 100 μm shown in **Table (S1-S5)**. The 1–100 μm range is considered representative of the bulk composition, while the 0.1 μm measurement reflects the near-surface region.

ICP-AES Measurements: Bulk 2D crystals of Nb: MoS₂ were processed in acid. That solution of acid was subsequently nebulized into an aerosol, which was then added to a high-energy plasma. The plasma stimulates the ions and atoms to a high-energy state.

As they return down to their normal states, they emit energy at wavelengths that are familiar to the specific element. In an optical chamber, the energy's wavelengths were separated. We calculated the amount of each element present quantitatively by tracking the wavelengths that are emitted. The concentration of Nb in Nb-doped MoS₂ is 0.583% as determined by ICP.

STEM Characterization: The exfoliated multilayer Nb-doped MoS₂ was transferred onto holey SiN TEM substrate with holes size of 1 μm (TED PAELLA). An aberration-corrected STEM (JEOL-ARM200F) furnished with a cold field emission gun and a DCOR probe corrector operating at 80 kV was utilized for HAADF-STEM imaging. HAADF and MAADF-STEM images were taken at semi-angles ranging between 68-280 mrad with a probe convergence of ≈ 30 mrad. The Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectra were collected across a 1 μm wide region using STEM.

To verify the quality, nature of crystals and thickness of flakes, Raman spectroscopy and atomic force microscopy (AFM) were utilized. Raman spectroscopy investigation was performed with a 532 nm wavelength excitation laser with a 1 μm spot. A WITec confocal Raman microscope (WITec alpha300 R, Ulm, Germany) with a 532 nm laser and a spectrometer with a thermoelectrically cooled CCD image sensor was used to record the Raman spectra. AFM was conducted using NT-MDT Ntegra Spectra in tapping mode, the measurement was carried out at room temperature using a 100X objective lens and a laser power of less than 1.2 mW. A custom-built 5000 M spectrofluorometer was used to determine photoluminescence excitation (PLE) spectra. The excitation source was a steady-state laser-driven Xenon lamp.

Transport Measurements: Transport measurements were performed using a dual-channel Keysight B1500A semiconductor parameter analyzer at room temperature under high vacuum (10⁻⁶ bar), the low temperature was attained by liquid nitrogen. The carrier concentration and mobility of the device were evaluated by the DX-100 Hall effect measurements system by making four points of contacts in the Vander Pauw geometry of the bulk crystal. Measurements were conducted at room temperature by sweeping the ±500 mT magnetic field.

Results and Discussion

Characterization of Material: **Figure 1(a)** shows the optical image of Nb-doped MoS₂ transferred onto a holey SiN₃ TEM grid for STEM and EDX with region-1 and region-2. **Figure 1(b)** shows large-area HAADF-STEM images of the multilayer Nb-doped MoS₂ sample, revealing the expected hexagonal lattice structure. Due to the similar scattering cross-sections of Nb and Mo, individual Nb dopants cannot be distinguished from the Mo host atom in Z-contrast imaging. Nevertheless, we did not identify any Nb substitution at sulfur sites (**Figure 1(c)** and **Figure S1 (b,c)**), which would otherwise result in increased contrast at the S atomic columns. To confirm the incorporation of Nb dopants, we acquired the EDX spectra of the suspended sample (**Figure 1(d-e)**). The EDX spectrum exhibits a small peak at ~ 16.4 keV, corresponding to the Nb K α_1 peak. The low intensity of Nb K α_1 is consistent with the nominal Nb doping concentration of 0.6%, which is near the detection limit of our system, suggesting that the Nb concentration in our system is \approx 0.55%. The EDX spectrum of region-1 is shown in **Figure S1(d,e)**. SIMS was performed to determine the sample's elemental composition at different depths. **Figure S1(f)** presents the near-surface and bulk compositions, highlighting notable differences. The Nb concentration near the surface is 0.49% and for the bulk crystal is 0.561%. The near-surface region exhibits a higher O₂ content, likely due to surface oxidation, and a lower Nb concentration than the bulk. The detailed description of five different samples (crystals) is shown in Supplementary information in tabular form. It suggests possible Nb diffusion during crystal growth or surface depletion effects. The final device was fabricated using exfoliated flakes, so its composition is expected to be closer to the near-surface region. The Nb doping percentage examined by EDX, ICP, Hall and SIMS is shown in **Figure 1(f)**, which looks almost similar to each other.

Figure 1: (a) Optical image of Nb-doped MoS₂ transferred onto a holey SiN₃ TEM grid for EDX with region-1 and region-2. (b) HAADF STEM image of multilayer Nb-doped MoS₂, with the corresponding FFT shown in the inset. (c) Magnified HAADF-STEM images highlight the integrated image intensity within the white rectangular region, where the Mo column shows consistently higher intensity than the S₂ column. (d) EDX spectrum. (e) EDX spectrum acquired from ~1 μm² region of the suspended sample (Zoom in view). (f) Comparison of EDX, ICP, Hall measurements and SIMS for Nb concentration.

Figure 2(a) displays the schematic illustration of the device based on the homojunction of Nb-doped MoS₂. **Figure 2 (b)** shows the optical image of the fabricated device, through the conventional viscoelastic stamping method by utilizing (PDMS). The desired flakes were transferred on a Si/SiO₂ substrate that consisted of pre-patterned metal contacts of Silver (Ag). The primary goal was identifying thick/thin layer homojunction with a well-defined interface on the substrate. The Raman spectra of pristine MoS₂, thin and thick sides of Nb-doped MoS₂ represented in **Figure 2(c)**, where two dominant modes E_{12g} and A_{1g} are shown respectively [33]. For pristine MoS₂, E_{12g} is located at 380.4 cm⁻¹ and A_{1g} is located at 405.8 cm⁻¹, the E_{12g} is located at 382.42 cm⁻¹ for both Nb-doped MoS₂ thin and thick flake sides. The A_{1g} mode of the thin layer is located at 407.12 cm⁻¹, but the A_{1g} mode of the thick layered is shifted to a higher wave number which is located at 408.24 cm⁻¹. This shows the blue shift and represents the p-

type behavior of the thicker flake side [34]. In **Figure 2(d)**, PL spectra reveal a high emission for the thin layer at 1.82 eV and 1.84 eV for the thick flake. The thick flake peak becomes broader which is more obvious, and also shows that Nb-doping will efficiently tune the electronic structure of MoS₂ [35]. The reduced PL intensity with greater thickness of Nb-MoS₂ represents a transition of band structure [34]. The blue shift of Raman and PL peaks endorses the tensile strain of the Nb doping effect [36]. This might be attributed to the nonuniform strain field in the crystal domain [37]. **Figure 2(e,f)** represents the AFM image and height profile of thin and thick flake sides. X-ray diffraction (XRD) of bulk pristine MoS₂ and Nb-doped MoS₂ is shown in **Figure S2**. The XRD pattern of the bulk material shows sharp diffraction peaks, confirming a successful synthesis of MoS₂ and Nb-doped MoS₂ (ICSD 01-075-1539). There is a slight shift due to substitutional doping during growth. As Nb has similar atomic radii to Mo, it is more likely to replace Mo atoms, and as it has slightly higher radii, the structure would have higher interplanar spacing. As a result, there is a slight shift in the XRD patterns.

Figure 2: (a) Schematic of the device based on thick/thin layered Nb-doped MoS₂-based homojunction. (b) Optical image of thick/thin homojunction of Nb-doped MoS₂ with silver (Ag) metal electrode. (c) Raman

spectra of homojunction Nb-doped MoS₂. (d) PL spectra of Nb-MoS₂ homojunction. (e,f) AFM image of the height profile of thick and thin flake sides.

Electrical Measurement: We have performed the electrical testing of the device based on the homojunction of Nb-doped MoS₂ (thick-thin). **Figure 3(a)** represents the I-V characteristic curves at different backgated voltages (V_g) with V_{ds} ranging from -2V to +2V. The output characteristics of the vdW homojunction p-n diode are simply examined using the I-V relation as fundamental p-n diodes [38].

$$I_{ds} = I_s \left[\exp\left(\frac{qV}{\eta k_B T}\right) - 1 \right] \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Here, I_s is the saturated current, q is the electronic charge, η represents the ideality factor, and k is the Boltzmann constant. **Figure 3(b)** represents the I-V curves with a logarithmic scale for homojunction p-n diode. To evaluate the current rectification effect, we checked the rectification ratio (R. R= I_f/I_r) as the ratio between forward current (I_f) and reverse bias current (I_r). Effectually, sweeping the V_g yields the highest rectification ratio of 1.05x10⁴ at V_g=-30V. The alteration in the rectification ratio with V_g for homojunction is illustrated in **Figure 3(c)**. When V_g < 0 V, the large barrier height is responsible for the reverse bias leakage current. In a similar vein, a negative V_g broadens the depletion region and raises the barrier height. Additionally, the modulation of the Schottky barrier (SB) height at the metal/TMDC interface by the gate voltage further enhances the rectification ratio. The silver (Ag) was used as metal contact which allows for efficient hole injection into the p-type Nb-MoS₂ thick layer and still has enough electron injection into the thin-layer n-type region, Ag can provide reasonably balanced carrier injection due to tunnelling effects and reduced contact resistance, facilitating efficient transport across the homojunction. Here, Ag is suitable for both p- and n-type MoS₂ (homojunction) due to doping, thickness dependency and good interface quality [39]. Meanwhile, in the case of thin n-type MoS₂, Ag enables moderate electron injection Schottky barrier, thus enabling asymmetric charge transport. This barrier inhibits electron conduction in the reverse bias but allows effective hole conduction in the forward bias, thus improving rectification behaviour. The inclusion of this asymmetrical charge injection with the band alignment of the homojunction could be the reason for the resulting high rectification ratio (~10⁴) and

ideality factor (1.23), suggesting highly efficient carrier transport. On the other side, device-2 showed the hole carriers are dominant as characteristics shown in **Figure S3 (a-d)**, and the threshold voltage changed to a positive region, due to Nb doping in MoS₂, reduced electron concentration and the source-drain current (I_{ds}) is decreased by two orders ^[40] and the rectification ratio of device-2 based on Nb-doped MoS₂ reduced to 10². The resistivity, conductivity, carrier concentration, Hall mobility and Hall Coefficient of bulk crystal are represented in **Table S6**. The ideality factor was extracted in **Figure S4**, the lowest value of the ideality factor (η) is 1.23, which is attained at $V_g = -30$ V. **Figure 3(d)** shows thickness modulated homojunction since the energy band gap (E_g) relies on the number of layers ^[41], minor E_g leads to decrease the width of tunnelling barrier and greater E_g in the channel helps to reduce the off-state current. Due to homojunction, the problem of interface traps may be ignored without any interface engineering. Irrespective of the homojunction, the edges created on the multilayer side, as illustrated in **Figure 3(d)**, should be taken into account since the band configuration at the homojunction is significantly influenced by its edge states. Remarkably, the FET characteristics displayed the shift from p to n-type behavior when the layer number was reduced ^[42]. Mechanical exfoliation also introduces strain effects that alter the band structure, shifting the Fermi level towards the conduction band. The p-type to n-type transition is significant in an attempt to obtain a naturally occurring homojunction with successful band-to-band tunnelling. When the number of layers is decreased, the electron concentration from the S vacancy exceeds the holes from Nb doping, resulting in n-type behaviour. The relationship between the homojunction's thick and thin parts is seen in **Figure 3(e)**. As the +ive V_g increases, the Fermi energy level shifts upward, causing the thin layer to behave eminently n-type. **Figure 3(f)** illustrates how the Fermi energy level keeps shifting higher when V_g rises to negative. The thick MoS₂ layer, in this case, shows typical p-type conduction behaviour. Therefore, the band structure becomes steeper as the barrier height between the thick and thin layers rises.

Figure 3: (a) I-V (linear scale) of the homojunction P-N diode based on Nb-doped MoS₂ at various V_g 's. (b) I-V curves at the logarithmic scale to obtain the rectification ratio (R.R). (c) Variation in the "R.R" with V_{bg} applied. (d) Homo-junction interface based on Nb-doped MoS₂. (e-f) Energy band diagram of MoS₂ homojunction under the varied gate with fixed bias, the transport phenomenon of the carriers of homojunction at different V_g 's.

We have examined the I-V characteristics of the device at low temperatures (180-250K) with $V_g=0$ and only a minimal decrease in the I_{ds} of the device was observed as demonstrated in **Figure 4(a,b)**. We have observed the negative differential resistance (NDR) effect in the device as represented in **Figure 4(c)** at different V_g values. The NDR effect arises due to charge trapping in defect states, tunneling mechanisms and quantum confinement effects in the material system [43]. The observed NDR in the homojunction p-n diode of Nb-doped MoS₂ originates primarily from the trap-assisted tunneling and thermionic emission mechanisms that dominate carrier transport under specific thermal conditions [44]. At a critical temperature ($T = 250$ K), the thermal energy becomes sufficient to activate charge carriers, leading to a sharp increase in conductivity. The emergence of the NDR effect at 250K can be attributed to an optimal balance between thermal activation and carrier trapping. At 250K, thermal energy overcomes the potential barrier for charge transport, allowing carriers to escape trapping centers and contributing to conduction,

triggering NDR. At this temperature, the shallow and intermediate trap states in the Nb: MoS₂ bandgap are efficiently activated, facilitating enhanced tunneling and recombination processes. However, as the temperature decreases further ($T = 160$ K), the charge carriers become localized due to reduced thermal energy, suppressing the NDR effect, the detailed form is shown graphically in **Figure S5 (a-i)**. Below 160 K, carrier freeze-out occurs, where thermal energy is insufficient to maintain delocalized transport, leading to carrier localization and suppression of NDR, at cryogenic temperatures, defects and disorder dominate, disrupting ballistic transport needed for NDR [44, 45]. We have also checked the NDR effect at different gate voltage ranges -50 V to $+50$ V and $T=220$ K. At $V_g=-50$ V, the device showed minimal I_{ds} and no NDR effect was observed. The NDR effect was prominent at positive gate voltages because of the quantum mechanical tunnelling effect. Typically, NDR is seen at a certain back gate voltage when the energy bands are uniquely aligned (e.g., resonant tunnelling or band-to-band tunnelling). This alignment occurs when the potential barrier across the junction and the Fermi levels are aligned by the gate voltage so that the current drops as the voltage rises because there are fewer states available for tunnelling. Nb doping introduces shallow donor states that increase carrier density, modify band alignment by making NDR sensitive to gate voltage and create defect-assisted tunneling paths which potentially lead to NDR [46]. As schematically shown in **Figure 4(d)**, At low temperatures, the device showed no current at $V_g < -50$ V, though at -50 V $< V_g < -25$ V, a minor BTBT tunneling current seemed at reverse bias, and when $V_g > -25$ V an NDR trend appeared by alteration from BTBT current to diffusion current, which is manifest at the forward bias region. These outcomes denote that the band arrangement of the homojunction of Nb-doped MoS₂ TFET can be tuned from Type-II to III by a back gate voltage. Additionally, to clarify the tuning of band configuration, the BTBT onset voltage (V_{BTBT}) is defined as the voltage at ($\approx 10^{-12}$ A) value of current and is scaled to the band offset among conduction band maxima (CBM) of thin MoS₂ and the valence band maximum (VBM) of thick MoS₂, as represented by the arrow in **Figure 4(d)**. As V_g increased, the band configuration changed from type-II to type-III, supporting the idea of the formation of a homojunction in a single flake of Nb-doped MoS₂. Furthermore, for the on-current, one important thing is that the BTBT current at the reverse bias is less than the diffusion current at the forward bias. Regarding the NDR

trend, the forward bias side clearly shows the trace of the changeover point from the BTBT current to the diffusion current. The tunneling current rises, and the Fermi level in the n-MoS₂ channel decreases as V_g increases. As the negative V_g increased, the NDR trend weakened and eventually vanished beyond -25 V.

Figure 4: (a) Low-temperature measurement of the device-based homojunction Nb-doped MoS₂. (b) NDR effect as the function of the temperature: inset shows the zoom-in view of NDR signal. (c) The NDR effect as the function of V_g : inset represent the zoom-in view of NDR signal. (d) Energy band diagrams at different V_g 's.

Furthermore, the light-matter interaction in homojunction Nb-MoS₂ devices is extremely intriguing to explore quantum efficiency and photoresponsivity. The optical response of the p-n diode under the various wavelengths and incident powers is demonstrated. With its tendency for on/off photo-switching, the photodetector exhibits high stability and reliability. The schematic illustration of the photocurrent investigation setup is shown in **Figure 5(a)**, where the FET is positioned in the glass chamber. Light of different wavelengths directed incident on the homojunction, causing to generate a prominent number of electron-hole pairs. These photo-induced charge carriers tunnel the barrier to produce efficient photoresponse. As shown in **Figure 5(b)**, the maximum photocurrent is about 415 nA at $V_g = +50$ V. The photocurrent (I_{ph}) variation was measured at $V_{ds} = 2$ V and $V_g = -50$ V, 0 V and +50 V. **Figure 5(c)** shows the photocurrent findings

obtained with $V_{ds} = 0.5$ to 2 V. As shown in **Figure 5(d)**, we have also examined the photoresponse at several other wavelengths (370, 405, 430, 530, 525, 730, and 970 nm). At 625 nm, the device exhibits a prominent photocurrent and decreases at higher wavelengths. The detailed photoresponse at each wavelength is presented in **Figure S6(a-f)**, individually. At 625 nm, the photon energy is around 1.98 eV, which is higher than the bandgap of MoS_2 , allowing for efficient absorption and generation of electron-hole pairs, leading to a significant photocurrent. Occasionally, the photoresponse drops because the semiconductor material has a lower absorption coefficient at longer wavelengths, which leads to less photon absorption and the creation of electron-hole pairs. The decrease in photocurrent at wavelengths higher than 625 nm is primarily due to the reduced photon energy, which becomes insufficient to excite carriers across the bandgap of the Nb-doped MoS_2 homojunction. This results in less efficient absorption and lower photocarrier generation. Moreover, doping effects and possible trap states could exacerbate this reduction in photocurrent at longer wavelengths. Additionally, the device's photoresponse was investigated at various incident light power densities (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and mW/cm^2). As incident power rises, the device displays higher photocurrent values, as seen in **Figure 5(e)**. This implies that at greater power intensities, the rate of electron-hole pair creation exceeds the rate of recombination. Consequently, it suggests that the photogenerated carriers may have a higher percentage of carriers before recombining with defects and capturing sites, which may contribute to the photocurrent. Higher quantum efficiency, which raises the photoresponse by absorbing and converting a larger proportion of input photons into electron-hole pairs, may sometimes result from higher power intensities. The value of short circuit current (I_{sc}) is 11 nA as shown in **Figure 5(f)**. The capability of a device to convert incident light into an electrical signal is measured by its responsivity (R). It exemplifies the connection between the input optical power and the resultant electrical output of the photodetector. Responsivity (R) of 1.09×10^3 A/W is calculated by the below equation [47]:

$$R = \frac{I_{ph}}{PA} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

where I_{ph} is mentioned as photocurrent, P is the light power density, and A is the effective area of the channel. The EQE value is examined by light absorption and the

buildup of photo-generated carriers. The extracted EQE is about 2.16×10^5 (%) by utilizing the below equation [47].

$$EQE = R \frac{hc}{e\lambda} \% \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

The h is Planck's constant, the speed of light (c), an electron's charge (e) and λ is the wavelength of light respectively. Detectivity (D^*) is a measure of a photodetector's sensitivity, which may be calculated as $D^* = RA^{1/2}/(2e \cdot I_{\text{dark}})^{1/2}$ [48]. D^* is about 7.5×10^{10} Jones. The rise/decay times were calculated by fitting the data gained through photocurrent measurements. The rise time is 14 ms and the decay time is 18 ms correspondingly, the detailed findings and equations are signified in **Figure S7 (a, b)**. The change of R w.r.t. wavelength is presented in **Figure 5(g)**; the device showed the maximum responsivity at $\lambda=625$ nm. The device showed an increasing trend in the photocurrent as the power of incident light increased as shown in **Figure 5(h)**. Across the homojunction, there is a locally created built-in potential caused by the variations in the bandgaps of thick-thin areas. The separation of charge carriers produced by the incident light is caused by this potential. To assess the source of the produced photocurrent for the fabricated device, scanning photocurrent mapping (SPCM) was employed. I_{ds} was measured as a laser beam ($\lambda = 625$ nm, $P = 6.73$ mW/cm²) scanned over the Nb: MoS₂ homojunction. The photocurrent mapping was attained under the existence of an external bias $V_{\text{ds}}=2$ V, revealed in **Figure 5(i)**, in which we can see the effective area of the produced photocurrent.

Figure 5: (a) Schematic illustration of the device for photoresponse. (b) Photocurrent at $V_g = -50$ V, 0, +50 V with $V_{ds} = 2$ V at wavelength 625 nm with the power 6 mW/cm^2 . (c) Photocurrent at $V_{ds} = 0.5, 1, 1.5$ and 2 V with wavelength 625 nm. (d) Photocurrent observation at various wavelengths (370-970 nm) of incident light. (e) Photocurrent at different powers of the incident light ($1-6 \text{ mW/cm}^2$). (f) I-V current dark and light to check the I_{sc} . (g) R Vs Wavelength. (h) I_{ph} vs Power. (i) Photocurrent mapping by SPCM.

Sr. No	Materials	Method	Wavelength (λ)	R (A/W)	D*(Jones)	Bias Voltage(v)	EQE	Ref
1	Nb-MoS ₂ /MoS ₂	CVD: Nb Doped	550 nm	51.4	3x10 ¹²	8	11.65x10 ³ %	[17]
2	MoS ₂ /p-MoS ₂	Mechanical exfoliation	500 nm	5.07	5 × 10 ¹⁰	1.5	7x10 ³ %	[49]
3	p-MoS ₂ /MoS ₂	CVD/nitrogen doping	532 nm	48.5	~10 ⁹	-10	11.301x10 ³ %	[21]
4	MoS ₂ /n-Si	precursor solution-annealing	650nm	11.9	2.1 × 10 ¹⁰	-2	--	[20]
5	Intrinsic MoS ₂ phototransistor	CVD	530 nm	0.05	2x10 ¹⁰	+1	11.7%	[50]
6	Nb: Doped MoS₂ Homojunction	CVT/ Mechanical Exfoliation	625 nm	1.09 x10³	7.5x10¹⁰	+2 V	2.16x10⁵ %	This Work

Table: Performance evaluation of MoS₂-based conventional FETs

Thickness-dependent Avalanche effect in Homojunction p-n diode MoS₂

Here, we have investigated the electrical breakdown in Nb-MoS₂ doped homojunction FETs with various channels and different thicknesses. The examined electrical breakdown of Nb: MoS₂ FETs under external E-fields is accredited to the impact ionization in the Nb: MoS₂-channel, which is avalanche multiplication. The critical electrical field (E_{CR}) and impact ionization rate (α) are the specific parameters, which are referred as the lowest E-field needed for the avalanche multiplication and number of electron-hole pairs generated per unit distance travelled by a hot carrier, correspondingly. Specifically, a substantial reliance of E_{CR} and α on the MoS₂ layer's thickness was directly linked to the quantum confinement effect that was shown in 2D systems. **Figure 6(a)** represents the avalanche effect which occurred at 23 V at $V_g=0$, where the avalanche region is highlighted in the circle, inset shows the optical image device that was investigated for avalanche effect. **Figure 6(b)** displays the optical images of fabricated device-2 before and after breakdown. In this device, the avalanche effect was observed at a relatively low voltage. However, as the voltage was further increased, the device experienced a thermal breakdown and subsequently burned out. We have achieved the

impact ionization very early as compared to the bulk devices as shown in **Figure 6(c)**. For the thicker device, the electrical breakdown occurred a little bit late at higher voltages (25 V) as shown in **Figure 6(d)**, the inset shows the optical image of device-3. Without any bias, the interdiffusion of the electron and hole emerges at the interface of the homojunction which leads to the bending of the energy band and creates the built-in electric field (E-field). After applying high biasing, the potential difference further rises and the built-in electric field overlaps the initial electric field until the width of the barrier, as shown in **Figure 6(e)**, then carrier multiplication occurs which leads to the avalanche effect. It is important to note that after threshold voltage, the avalanche effect and BBT dominate the current transport. Realizing high performance requires a careful examination of the competing dynamic between avalanche and BBT dark current under high bias ^[51]. The device-4 is shown in **Figure 6(f)**, which contains the thick-thin junction of Nb-doped MoS₂. In this device, we have checked the avalanche mechanism in dark and under light as well. The avalanche breakdown mechanism occurred early under the laser light, which shows the power-efficient device. **Figure 6(g)** represents the dark current (I_{dark}) and under illumination with the radiant light of a wavelength of 625 nm at $V_g=0$. I_{ph} shows electrical breakdown at a voltage lower than the onset voltage of the dark current's breakdown, the output curves were less steep. This can be accredited to the smaller value of an electric field that the charge carrier feels in the channel arising from the earlier onset of breakdown behaviour (smaller voltage). Furthermore, increased thickness of the flake causes to increase in the breakdown voltage, but doping causes a reduction in the breakdown voltage due to high carrier density. We conclude that the thick-thin junction reached to early avalanche breakdown as compared to the thicker-thick (Multilayer) homojunction (Device-1 and 3) of Nb-doped MoS₂. The greater electric field concentration in the thin region is the main cause of the earlier avalanche breakdown in the thick-thin junction of Nb-doped MoS₂ as opposed to the thick-thick (multilayer) junction. Early avalanche breakdown results from the high electric field's ability to accelerate carriers to higher energies more rapidly, which raises the possibility of impact ionization and carrier multiplication. The early breakdown in the thick-thin structure is also influenced by doping, defect states, and thermal effects. The Fermi level of the thick layer shifted downward as the layer thickness rises as shown in **Figure 6(h)**. **Figure 6(i)** shows

the band bending of and photocarrier transport behavior of a thick-thin junction. The thick/thin layer bends downward/upward suggestively. It gives rise to a potential barrier in the conduction band, which denies the electron transport from thick to thin layers of Nb-doped MoS₂. For this reason, the thick layer side gives smaller contribution to the photoresponse of the device. These characteristics lead to understanding the rectifying behavior of device. When the device is positively biased the conduction band of the thin layer is raised and the electron barrier will be smaller, which helps to the forward conduction behavior. In the breakdown region, the current boosts to a high level under illumination. Under illumination, the photogenerated carrier can accelerate through the high-field region, which favours the impact ionization phenomenon ^[52]. Our study suggests a simple and effective technique for improving the performance of 2D-TMDC-based devices. Our work sheds light on the electrical breakdown of Nb: MoS₂ at both high and low fields. It also contributes to a better understanding of atomically thin avalanche FETs and photodetectors, which is an emerging field in 2D optoelectronics research.

Figure 6: (a) I_{ds} - V_{ds} characteristics of Nb-doped FET measured at $V_g=0$. The dashed line indicates the breakdown voltage, which is 23 V: inset displays the optical image of device-1 represents the avalanche effect. (b) Optical image of the device-2 as fabricated and in burnt state. (c) The avalanche breakdown mechanism of device-2 is based on the Nb-doped MoS_2 channel; the electrical breakdown occurred very early. (d) The avalanche effect in device-3 shows that the thicker device can sustain the greater voltage, the avalanche phenomenon started at 25 V. (e) Band structure at high bias. (f) The optical image of device-4, as fabricated. (g) The avalanche mechanism is in-dark and under radiant light of a wavelength of 625 nm. (h) Band alignment of thick-thin Nb-doped MoS_2 before contact. (i) Energy band diagram and photo-carrier transport.

Conclusion

In summary, we have grown Nb-doped MoS₂ by CVT technique, a method for producing heteroatom-doped TMDC crystals is offered by the presented Nb-doping, which uses pre-Nb metal as the precursor and the p-type doping. The lateral homojunction Nb-doped MoS₂ (Thick-thin) was examined to estimate the current rectification ratio ($\sim 10^4$) and photodetection mechanism. Our findings showed that negative differential resistance (NDR) is field-dependent and occurs at low temperatures. The photodetection and tunability of Nb-doped MoS₂ homojunction-based devices were thoroughly examined. Electrical testing demonstrates that the p-type doping effect induced by Nb doping in device-2 leads to a reduction in electron concentration. According to studies on the tunability of MoS₂ homojunction-based devices, the external electric field can significantly influence the photoresponse and detectivity. The device shows a maximum photoresponsivity of 1.09×10^3 A/W, the external quantum efficiency (EQE) is 2.16×10^5 % and detectivity (D^*) is 7.5×10^{10} Jones. We also checked the avalanche mechanism in various devices based on Nb-doped MoS₂. As a result, the breakdown voltage rises with increasing flake thickness, while the breakdown voltage falls with doping because of the high carrier density. Thus, our work introduces the function of 2D materials in avalanche devices by presenting a straightforward and reliable technique to investigate carrier multiplication in homojunction p-n diodes.

Author's Contribution

E.E, KJS and Z.S have designed the project, E.E, KJS and UA have done device fabrication, electrical measurements and analyzed the data, PC has employed XRD, and PPM has performed SIMS analysis. MFK and JA have done a formal analysis of the whole experiment. Y.C. performed TEM imaging under the supervision of G.E. M.L. performed ICP measurements. Z.S: supervision and project funding and growth crystals. All authors wrote the final manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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References

- [1] G. Bedi, G. K. Venayagamoorthy, R. Singh, R. R. Brooks, K.-C. Wang, *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* **2018**, 5, 847.
- [2] H. Y. Jeong, U. J. Kim, H. Kim, G. H. Han, H. Lee, M. S. Kim, Y. Jin, T. H. Ly, S. Y. Lee, Y.-G. Roh, *ACS nano* **2016**, 10, 8192.
- [3] T. Roy, M. Tosun, X. Cao, H. Fang, D.-H. Lien, P. Zhao, Y.-Z. Chen, Y.-L. Chueh, J. Guo, A. Javey, *ACS nano* **2015**, 9, 2071.
- [4] E. Elahi, M. Ahmad, A. Dahshan, M. Rabeel, S. Saleem, H. Hegazy, S. Aftab, *Nanoscale* **2024**, 16, 14.
- [5] Z. Xu, R. Zheng, A. Khanaki, Z. Zuo, J. Liu, *Applied Physics Letters* **2015**, 107.
- [6] D. Pierucci, H. Henck, C. H. Naylor, H. Sediri, E. Lhuillier, A. Balan, J. E. Rault, Y. J. Dappe, F. Bertran, P. L. Fèvre, *Scientific reports* **2016**, 6, 26656.
- [7] Y. Gong, J. Lin, X. Wang, G. Shi, S. Lei, Z. Lin, X. Zou, G. Ye, R. Vajtai, B. I. Yakobson, *Nature materials* **2014**, 13, 1135.
- [8] E. Elahi, M. Rabeel, B. Ahmed, J. Aziz, M. Suleman, M. A. Khan, S. Rehman, A. Rehmat, M. Asim, M. A. Rehman, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2024**, 16, 54367.
- [9] E. Elahi, S. Nisar, M. Rabeel, A. A. Al-Kahtani, M. W. Iqbal, M. Irfan, M. Abubakr, J. Aziz, G. Dastgeer, *Available at SSRN 4525475*.
- [10] C.-H. Lee, G.-H. Lee, A. M. Van Der Zande, W. Chen, Y. Li, M. Han, X. Cui, G. Arefe, C. Nuckolls, T. F. Heinz, *Nature nanotechnology* **2014**, 9, 676.
- [11] J. Appenzeller, Y.-M. Lin, J. Knoch, P. Avouris, *Physical review letters* **2004**, 93, 196805.
- [12] K. Kato, K.-W. Jo, H. Matsui, H. Tabata, T. Mori, Y. Morita, T. Matsukawa, M. Takenaka, S. Takagi, *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices* **2020**, 67, 1880.
- [13] a)X. Cong, Y. Zheng, F. Huang, Q. You, J. Tang, F. Fang, K. Jiang, C. Han, Y. Shi, *Nano Research* **2022**, 15, 8442; b)Y. Sato, T. Nishimura, D. Duanfei, K. Ueno, K. Shinokita, K. Matsuda, K. Nagashio, *Advanced Electronic Materials* **2021**, 7, 2100292.
- [14] P. Chava, Z. Fekri, Y. Vekariya, T. Mikolajick, A. Erbe, *Applied Physics Reviews* **2023**, 10.
- [15] Y. H. Kim, W. Jiang, D. Lee, D. Moon, H. Y. Choi, J. C. Shin, Y. Jeong, J. C. Kim, J. Lee, W. Huh, *Advanced Materials* **2024**, 2314274.
- [16] a)M.-C. Chang, P.-H. Ho, M.-F. Tseng, F.-Y. Lin, C.-H. Hou, I.-K. Lin, H. Wang, P.-P. Huang, C.-H. Chiang, Y.-C. Yang, *Nature communications* **2020**, 11, 3682; b)B. Cao, Z. Wang, X. Xiong, L. Gao, J. Li, M. Dong, *New Journal of Chemistry* **2021**, 45, 12033.
- [17] R. Tao, X. Qu, Z. Wang, F. Li, L. Yang, J. Li, D. Wang, K. Zheng, M. Dong, *Journal of Materials Science & Technology* **2022**, 119, 61.
- [18] S. B. Desai, S. R. Madhupathy, A. B. Sachid, J. P. Llinas, Q. Wang, G. H. Ahn, G. Pitner, M. J. Kim, J. Bokor, C. Hu, *Science* **2016**, 354, 99.
- [19] J. Ma, X. Chen, Y. Sheng, L. Tong, X. Guo, M. Zhang, C. Luo, L. Zong, Y. Xia, C. Sheng, *Journal of Materials Science & Technology* **2022**, 106, 243.
- [20] Y. Zhang, Y. Yu, L. Mi, H. Wang, Z. Zhu, Q. Wu, Y. Zhang, Y. Jiang, *Small* **2016**, 12, 1062.
- [21] J. Lu, Z. Guo, W. Wang, J. Lu, Y. Hu, J. Wang, Y. Xiao, X. Wang, S. Wang, Y. Zhou, *Nanotechnology* **2020**, 32, 015701.
- [22] X. Luo, Z. Peng, Z. Wang, M. Dong, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2021**, 13, 59154.
- [23] S. Ahmed, X. Ding, P. P. Murmu, N. Bao, R. Liu, J. Kennedy, L. Wang, J. Ding, T. Wu, A. Vinu, *Small* **2020**, 16, 1903173.
- [24] X. Lu, M. Yan, Z. Yan, W. Chen, X. Sui, J. Hao, W. Liu, *Tribology International* **2021**, 156, 106844.
- [25] L. Tang, R. Xu, J. Tan, Y. Luo, J. Zou, Z. Zhang, R. Zhang, Y. Zhao, J. Lin, X. Zou, *Advanced Functional Materials* **2021**, 31, 2006941.

- [26] Z. Qin, L. Loh, J. Wang, X. Xu, Q. Zhang, B. Haas, C. Alvarez, H. Okuno, J. Z. Yong, T. Schultz, *ACS nano* **2019**, 13, 10768.
- [27] S. Wemple, W. Niehaus, H. Cox, J. Dilorenzo, W. Schlosser, *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices* **1980**, 27, 1013.
- [28] J. Bullock, M. Amani, J. Cho, Y.-Z. Chen, G. H. Ahn, V. Adinolfi, V. R. Shrestha, Y. Gao, K. B. Crozier, Y.-L. Chueh, *Nature Photonics* **2018**, 12, 601.
- [29] R. Yang, Z. Wang, P. X.-L. Feng, *Nanoscale* **2014**, 6, 12383.
- [30] E. Yalon, C. J. McClellan, K. K. Smithe, M. Muñoz Rojo, R. L. Xu, S. V. Suryavanshi, A. J. Gabourie, C. M. Neumann, F. Xiong, A. B. Farimani, *Nano letters* **2017**, 17, 3429.
- [31] J. Pak, Y. Jang, J. Byun, K. Cho, T.-Y. Kim, J.-K. Kim, B. Y. Choi, J. Shin, Y. Hong, S. Chung, *ACS nano* **2018**, 12, 7109.
- [32] B. Saha, P. Chakraborty, *Energy Procedia* **2013**, 41, 80.
- [33] Z. Wang, X. Xiong, J. Li, M. Dong, *Materials Today Physics* **2021**, 16, 100290.
- [34] K. P. Dhakal, D. L. Duong, J. Lee, H. Nam, M. Kim, M. Kan, Y. H. Lee, J. Kim, *Nanoscale* **2014**, 6, 13028.
- [35] P. Yang, A.-G. Yang, L. Chen, J. Chen, Y. Zhang, H. Wang, L. Hu, R.-J. Zhang, R. Liu, X.-P. Qu, *Nano Research* **2019**, 12, 823.
- [36] Y. Y. Hui, X. Liu, W. Jie, N. Y. Chan, J. Hao, Y.-T. Hsu, L.-J. Li, W. Guo, S. P. Lau, *ACS nano* **2013**, 7, 7126.
- [37] H. Kim, D. Ovchinnikov, D. Deiana, D. Unuchek, A. Kis, *Nano letters* **2017**, 17, 5056.
- [38] A. Kumar, S. Vinayak, R. Singh, *Current Applied Physics* **2013**, 13, 1137.
- [39] a)A. Allain, J. Kang, K. Banerjee, A. Kis, *Nature materials* **2015**, 14, 1195; b)S. Das, H.-Y. Chen, A. V. Penumatcha, J. Appenzeller, *Nano letters* **2013**, 13, 100.
- [40] a)P. Zhang, N. Cheng, M. Li, B. Zhou, C. Bian, Y. Wei, X. Wang, H. Jiang, L. Bao, Y. Lin, *ACS applied materials & interfaces* **2020**, 12, 18650; b)J. Suh, T. L. Tan, W. Zhao, J. Park, D.-Y. Lin, T.-E. Park, J. Kim, C. Jin, N. Saigal, S. Ghosh, *Nature communications* **2018**, 9, 199.
- [41] A. Kuc, N. Zibouche, T. Heine, *Physical Review B—Condensed Matter and Materials Physics* **2011**, 83, 245213.
- [42] N. Fang, S. Toyoda, T. Taniguchi, K. Watanabe, K. Nagashio, *Advanced Functional Materials* **2019**, 29, 1904465.
- [43] a)S. M. Sze, Y. Li, K. K. Ng, *Physics of semiconductor devices*, John Wiley & sons, **2021**; b)S. Fan, Q. A. Vu, S. Lee, T. L. Phan, G. Han, Y.-M. Kim, W. J. Yu, Y. H. Lee, *ACS nano* **2019**, 13, 8193.
- [44] a)M. Wang, C. Y. Wang, C. Wu, Q. Li, C. Pan, C. Wang, S. J. Liang, F. Miao, *Advanced Electronic Materials* **2019**, 5, 1800853; b)A. V. Bruce, S. Liu, J. N. Fry, H.-P. Cheng, *Physical Review B* **2020**, 102, 115415.
- [45] G. Woo, J. Cho, H. Yeom, M. Y. Yoon, G. W. Eom, M. Kim, J. Mun, H. C. Lee, H.-U. Kim, H. Yoo, *Small Science* **2024**, 4, 2300202.
- [46] a)R. Mitra, K. Iordanidou, N. Shetty, M. A. Hoque, A. Datta, A. Kalaboukhov, J. Wiktor, S. Kubatkin, S. P. Dash, S. Lara-Avila, *arXiv preprint arXiv:2409.04908* **2024**; b)Y. Tang, L. Gan, J. Feng, Y. Li, Y. Zhong, C. Ning, presented at *2023 Opto-Electronics and Communications Conference (OECC)*, **2023**.
- [47] E. Elahi, M. Ahmad, A. Dahshan, M. Rabeel, S. Saleem, V. H. Nguyen, H. Hegazy, S. Aftab, *Nanoscale* **2024**, 16, 14.
- [48] P. Wang, S. Liu, W. Luo, H. Fang, F. Gong, N. Guo, Z. G. Chen, J. Zou, Y. Huang, X. Zhou, *Advanced Materials* **2017**, 29, 1604439.
- [49] M. S. Choi, D. Qu, D. Lee, X. Liu, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, W. J. Yoo, *ACS nano* **2014**, 8, 9332.
- [50] Z. Yin, H. Li, H. Li, L. Jiang, Y. Shi, Y. Sun, G. Lu, Q. Zhang, X. Chen, H. Zhang, *ACS nano* **2012**, 6, 74.
- [51] J. Chen, J. Chen, X. Li, J. He, L. Yang, J. Wang, F. Yu, Z. Zhao, C. Shen, H. Guo, *NPJ Quantum Materials* **2021**, 6, 103.
- [52] H. Wang, H. Xia, Y. Liu, Y. Chen, R. Xie, Z. Wang, P. Wang, J. Miao, F. Wang, T. Li, *Nature Communications* **2024**, 15, 3639.